
THE INTERPLAY OF TRADITION AND TRANSFORMATION IN SHRI GANESH UTSAV: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY ANALYSIS OF CULTURAL, SOCIAL, AND ENVIRONMENTAL DIMENSIONS AMONG FAMILIES CELEBRATING GANESH IDOLS AT HOME**Dr. Babita H. Kakkar and Dr. Rajeshri Pravin Shinkar**

Assistant Professor, SIES (Nerul) College of Arts, Science and Commerce (Autonomous)

ABSTRACT

Shri Ganesh Utsav is a significant cultural and religious festival that is observed by many families and communities in India. This study examines the interplay between tradition and transformation in Shri Ganesh Utsav, with emphasis on the cultural, social and environmental aspects of celebrating Ganesh idols at home. Adopting a description quantitative research approach, primary data were collected through a structured Likert-scale questionnaire administered to residential respondents in Navi Mumbai. The survey captured the respondent's perceptions of traditional practices, modernization and technology, social unity, culture identity, environmental awareness and continuity of values. The study data were analyzed with descriptive statistical techniques, including mean score analysis, to assess perceptions across different aspects of the celebration. Comparative analysis was employed to examine variation across age groups, while correlation analysis was used to explore the relationship between environmental awareness and the adoption of eco-friendly practices. The findings show a strong adherence to traditional cultural and religious practices, highlighting the festival's enduring role of Shri Ganesh Utsav in preserving family-based traditions. Although modernization has influenced contemporary modes of celebration, the festival continues to play a vital role in sustaining cultural and religious traditional values. The celebration also promotes social cohesion and strengthens cultural identity, while families demonstrate a moderate adoption of environmentally friendly practices. Overall, the study highlights Shri Ganesh Utsav as a resilient cultural tradition that continues to adapt meaningfully to changing urban contexts without losing its core values.

Keywords: *Shri Ganesh Utsav, Tradition and Transformation, Cultural Identity, Modernization and Technology, Social Unity, Environmental Awareness*

1. INTRODUCTION

Shri Ganesh Utsav is one of the most important religious and cultural festivals in India, especially in Maharashtra and other regions with a strong cultural influence. Traditionally celebrated as a domestic ritual, the festival underwent a major transformation in the late 19th century when Lokmanya Bal Gangadhar Tilak popularized its public celebration to promote social unity and nationalist consciousness during the colonial period. In contemporary times, Shri Ganesh Utsav has evolved further. The integration of modern elements such as large-scale public structures, digital media, environmental awareness campaigns and community and social initiatives. This transformation reflects a dynamic interaction between tradition and modernity, making the festival an important subject for culture and social analysis.

Statement of the Problem

Although Shri Ganesh Utsav remains deeply rooted in tradition, celebrations often reflect commercialization, technological influence and changing social priorities. These transformations raise questions about their impact on the festival's cultural essence, social functions and cultural values. It is therefore, necessary to examine whether Shri Ganesh Utsav continues to serve as a unifying cultural and social institution in the present context.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Deborah De Koning (2023). Research provides a theoretical framing for environmental transformation and ritual innovation. The study analyses how eco- friendly materials and practices are incorporated in Ganesh Chaturthi, representing a Green Hindu identity.

Nikita Mohta (2024). The study provides the historical context for tradition and public transformation. It traces the historical transformation of Ganesh Utsav from private ritual to public political tool during the Indian independence movement.

Jitendrakumar A. Patel (2024). The document provides general information about the environmental aspects of Ganesh Utsav rituals and challenges. The study explains how traditional rituals align with ecological sustainability, and how modernization has an impact on environmental practices.

The CSR Journal (2024). The article is directly related to environmental awareness and the transformation in festival practices. The study reports on the eco-centric initiatives that encourage sustainable Ganesh Utsav celebrations.

V. S. Anisha & O. Reegan (2024). The article supports the dimension of social unity and cultural identity in the festival studies and analyses how festivals operate like cultural diplomacy, which promotes social harmony and identity beyond the local boundaries.

International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research (2025). The study links directly into environmental awareness and sustainable transformation and highlights how traditional clay idols support environmental sustainability as compared to PoP idols.

Artti Devi & Yograj Singh (2025). The study highlights the role of festivals (including Ganesh Utsav) in cultural continuity and social unity. The Study observed that Indian festivals preserve the heritage, promote social cohesion, and contribute to national identity.

Times of India Reports (2025). The report illustrates current social trends toward sustainability in festival celebrations. The study includes news coverage of the increase of green practices (for example, green idols, reduction of noise, traditional instruments). **Times of India (2025).** The report highlights the relationship between traditional festival practices and emerging concerns about sustainability and reports on Nagpur festival mandals for noise pollution reduction and embracing traditional practices.

Times of India (2025). The study shows how tradition interacts with contemporary cultural expression and documents how the local cultural narratives are integrated into the festival themes.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the role of Shri Ganesh Utsav in preserving traditional cultural and religious practices at the family level.
2. To analyze the impact of modernization and technology on the celebration of Shri Ganesh Utsav.
3. To study the role of Shri Ganesh Utsav in promoting social unity and cultural identity.
4. To examine the relationship between social and environmental awareness and changing practices of Shri Ganesh Utsav.
5. To understand how traditional values are maintained amid changing modes of celebration.

3.2 Hypotheses of the Study Hypothesis 1: Tradition Preservation

- **H₀₁:** Shri Ganesh Utsav does not significantly contribute to the preservation of traditional cultural and religious practices in families.
- **H₁₁:** Shri Ganesh Utsav significantly contributes to the preservation of traditional cultural and religious practices in families.

Hypothesis 2: Impact of Modernization

- **H₀₂:** Modernization and technology have no significant impact on how Shri Ganesh Utsav is celebrated.
- **H₁₂:** Modernization and technological have a significant impact on how Shri Ganesh Utsav is celebrated.

Hypothesis 3: Social Unity and Cultural Identity

- **H₀₃:** Participation at Shri Ganesh Utsav does not significantly influence social unity and cultural identity in families and communities.
- **H₁₃:** Participation at Shri Ganesh Utsav significantly improves social unity and cultural identity in families and communities.

Hypothesis 4: Environmental and Social Awareness

- **H₀₄:** There is no significant relationship between environmental or social awareness and changing practices of Shri Ganesh Utsav celebrations.

- **H₁₄**: There is a significant relationship between environmental or social awareness and changing practices of Shri Ganesh Utsav celebrations.

Hypothesis 5: Continuity Amid Change

- **H₀₅**: Transformation in celebration practices have weakened the core cultural values of Shri Ganesh Utsav.
- **H₁₅**: Regardless of transformations in celebration practices, the core cultural values of Shri Ganesh Utsav remain strong and intact.

3.3 Significance of the study

This study is significant as it contributes to understanding of how cultural traditions adapt to social changes. It highlights the role of festivals such as Shri Ganesh Utsav in shaping social harmony while ensuring continuity of cultural values. The findings offer valuable insights for scholars of cultural studies, as well as community organizers, and cultural institutions involved in the festival planning.

3.4 Research Design and Data Sources

The study uses a descriptive quantitative research design and is based on both primary and secondary data sources.

Primary data were collected through a structured Likert-scale questionnaire consisting of 15 statements administered to families celebrating Shri Ganesh Utsav by placing Ganesh idols at home. The questionnaire was designed to measure respondents' perceptions related to traditional practices, modernization and technology, social unity, environmental awareness and the continuity of cultural values.

Secondary data were collected from relevant research articles, academic papers, and online sources related to Shri Ganesh Utsav.

3.5 Study Area, Sampling Technique and Sample Size

The study was conducted in residential areas of Navi Mumbai. A purposive sampling technique was used to select respondents from residential families celebrating Shri Ganesh Utsav with Ganesh idols at home. The sample size consisted of 30 respondent families.

3.6 Data Analysis

The data collected through questionnaires were analyzed using descriptive quantitative techniques, including mean score analysis. Comparative analysis was employed to examine variation across age groups in relation to modernization, technology and expenditure pattern. Correlation analysis was used to examine the relationship between environmental awareness and the adoption of eco-friendly practices during Shri Ganesh Utsav. The questionnaire responses were organized and presented through tables and graphical representations, such as bar charts and pie charts, to facilitate clear understanding and interpretation of the data.

3.7 Scope of the Study

The study focuses on household-level celebrations of Shri Ganesh Utsav in Navi Mumbai. It examines traditional practices, modernization and technology, social unity, environmental awareness, and the continuity of cultural values based on primary data.

3.8 Limitations of the Study

The study is limited to 30 respondent families from selected areas of Navi Mumbai. The findings are based on self-reported perceptions and do not include Sarvajanic (public) Ganesh mandal celebrations.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Age of Respondents

Table 4.1 Age of Respondents

Age Group	Responses	% Responses
Below 20	4	13.3
20 – 25	14	46.7
26 – 30	-	-
Above 30	12	40.0
Total	30	100%

Source: Primary Data

Figure 4.1 Age of Respondents

Source: Primary Data

INTERPRETATION

The age-wise distribution of respondents indicates that the largest proportion of participants belongs to the **20–25 age group (46.7%)** of the total respondents. Respondents **above 30 years** constitute **40%**, reflecting significant representation from more mature households actively involved in celebrating Shri Ganesh Utsav. A smaller share of respondents (**13.3%**) falls in the **below 20** age group, while no responses were recorded from the **26–30** age group. Overall, the sample reflects a balanced representation of younger and older age groups, allowing for meaningful comparison of perceptions across generations regarding the celebration practices of Shri Ganesh Utsav.

4.2 Gender of Respondents

Table 4.2 Gender of Respondents

Gender	Responses	% Responses
Male	9	30
Female	21	70
Total	30	100%

Source: Primary Data

Figure 4.2 Gender of Respondents

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

The gender-wise distribution of respondents shows a higher participation of female respondents, who constitute 70% of the total sample, while male respondents account for 30%. This indicates that women were more actively represented in the study, possibly reflecting their greater involvement in household-level planning and participation in Shri Ganesh Utsav celebrations. The gender composition of the sample provides valuable insights into domestic celebration practices, where women often play a central role in maintaining rituals and traditions.

4.3 Area of Residence of Respondents

Table 4.3 Area of Residence of Respondents

Area of Residence	Responses	% Responses
Vashi	2	6.7
Koparkhairane	-	-
Nerul	2	6.7
Seawoods	2	6.7
Ulwe	2	6.7
Sanpada	1	3.3
Belapur	1	3.3
Kharghar	11	36.7
Panvel	3	10.0
Airoli	1	3.3
Others	5	16.7
Total	30	100%

Source: Primary Data

Figure 4.3 Area of Residence of Respondents

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

The area-wise distribution of respondents indicates that Kharghar accounts for the highest share of respondents (36.7%), followed by Panvel (10%) and Other areas (16.7%). The remaining respondents are spread across various nodes of Navi Mumbai, each contributing a smaller percentage. This distribution reflects a geographically diverse sample, with representation from multiple residential areas of Navi Mumbai, allowing for a broader understanding of household-level celebration practices of Shri Ganesh Utsav across the region.

4.4 Traditional Practices of Shri Ganesh Utsav in Families

Table 4.4 Traditional Practices of Shri Ganesh Utsav in Families

Variables	Mean Score
Preserves traditional practices	4.8
Rituals are strictly followed	4.8
Strengthens cultural values	4.9

Source: Primary Data

Figure 4.4 Traditional Practices of Shri Ganesh Utsav in Families

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

The respondents believe that Shri Ganesh Utsav plays an important role in maintaining traditional cultural and religious practices in their family. An average score of above

4.8 indicates that rituals are followed regularly. This implies that in spite of change in lifestyle, the families continue to value and practice traditions during the festival. Thus, H_{11} is accepted, which indicates that Shri Ganesh Utsav contributes significantly to the preservation of traditional practices at the family level.

4.4.1 Modernization, Technology & Expenditure in Shri Ganesh Utsav Table 4.5.1 Modernization, Technology & Expenditure in Shri Ganesh Utsav

Variables	Mean Score
Use of technology	4.8
Modern adaptations	4.83
Modernization-driven spending	4.875

Source: Primary Data

Figure 4.5.1 Modernization, Technology & Expenditure in Shri Ganesh Utsav

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

Respondents agreed that the use of digital platforms, modern decor and online shopping improved the experience of the festival. Nevertheless, these have affected festive spending, indicating a change in consumption patterns of traditional rituals. The results support H_{12} , complying that the celebration of Shri Ganesh Utsav has been influenced by modernization and technology.

4.4.2 Age-wise Comparative Analysis of Modernization, Technology & Expenditure Pattern

Table 4.5.2 Age-wise Comparative Analysis of Modernization, Technology & Expenditure Pattern

Age Group	Use of Technology	Modern adaptations	Modernization-driven spending
Below 20	3.25	4.00	4.25
20–25	3.14	4.29	3.32
26–30	0.00	0.00	0.00
Above 30	3.58	4.17	3.42

Source: Primary Data

Figure 4.5.2 Age-wise Comparative Analysis of Modernization, Technology & Expenditure Pattern

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

The age-wise analysis shows noticeable differences in the adoption of technology and modern practices during Shri Ganesh Utsav. Younger age groups report higher mean scores for technology use and modernization-driven spending, while older respondents show relatively moderate adoption. This suggests that modernization is shaping celebration practices more strongly among younger households.

4.5 Social Unity and Cultural Identity during Shri Ganesh Utsav

Table 4.6 Social Unity and Cultural Identity during Shri Ganesh Utsav

Variables	Mean Score
Promotes social interaction & bonding	4.83
Strengthens cultural identity	4.77
Enhances social harmony & cohesion	4.83

Source: Primary Data

Figure 4.6 Social Unity and Cultural Identity during Shri Ganesh Utsav

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

The analysis shows that, Shri Ganesh Utsav is considered as a favorable occasion for cultural identity and social unity. A high average mean score denotes that the festival through interactions between neighbors and community members, reinforces a strong sense of cultural belonging within families. According to the respondents, the festival promotes social harmony. As a result, the findings accept H_{13} , which states that Shri Ganesh Utsav plays a key role in maintaining cultural identity and social cohesion.

4.7.1 Environmental and Social Awareness in Shri Ganesh Utsav Table 4.7.1 Environmental and Social Awareness in Shri Ganesh Utsav

Variables	Mean Score
Eco-friendly practices	4.60
Environmental awareness	4.17

Source: Primary Data

Figure 4.7.1 Environmental and Social Awareness in Shri Ganesh Utsav

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

The descriptive analysis shows a high mean score, which means that most respondents are aware of the impact of environmental awareness on the celebration of Shri Ganesh Utsav and suggest the adoption of ecological practices.

4.7.2 Correlation between Environmental Awareness and Eco-friendly Practices Table 4.7.2 Correlation between Environmental Awareness and Eco-friendly Practices

Variables	Eco-friendly practices	Environmental Awareness
Eco-friendly practices	1	0.483
Environmental Awareness	0.483	1

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

The analysis shows a positive correlation ($r = 0.483$) between ecological awareness and the adoption of environmentally responsible choices. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level. This means that green practices are common in families with higher level of environmental consciousness. Thus, H_{14} is accepted, which shows the significant relationship between environmental awareness and changing practices of Shri Ganesh Utsav celebration.

4.8 Continuity of Traditional Values in Shri Ganesh Utsav Table 4.8 Continuity of Traditional Values in Shri Ganesh Utsav

Variables	Mean Score
Essence of tradition remains intact	4.67
Core values are preserved	4.77
Meaningful family & community role	4.87
Tradition-modern balance	4.67

Source: Primary Data

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

The findings indicate strong agreement among respondents regarding the continuity of traditional values in Shri Ganesh Utsav. High mean scores suggest that despite the adoption of modern practices and technologies, the core cultural and religious essence of the festival remains intact. Respondents also perceive the festival as continuing to play a meaningful role in family and community life. The balanced integration of tradition and modern elements appears to contribute to the festival's relevance in contemporary society. Thus, H_{15} is accepted, confirming that traditional values of Shri Ganesh Utsav are sustained despite changing modes of celebration.

5. CONCLUSION

The study highlights the continued cultural significance of Shri Ganesh Utsav at the household level while reflecting its adaptation to contemporary social contexts. The findings reveal strong adherence to traditional religious and cultural practices, indicating that the festival remains an important medium for preserving inherited values and rituals within families. At the same time, modernization and technological influences have reshaped certain aspects of celebration, including modes of participation and expenditure, particularly among younger households.

The festival also plays a vital role in fostering social unity and reinforcing cultural identity, strengthening bonds within families and the wider community. Increasing environmental awareness has further influenced celebration practices, encouraging the adoption of eco-friendly measures without diminishing the festival's spiritual essence. Overall, the study demonstrates that Shri Ganesh Utsav successfully balances tradition and change, ensuring its continued relevance in contemporary society while sustaining its core cultural and religious values.

REFERENCES

- [1] Anisha, V. S., & Reegan, O. (2024). Festivals as Soft Power: Enhancing Cultural Identity. *ShodhKosh Journal of Visual & Performing Arts*.
- [2] Artti Devi & Yograj Singh. (2025). Living Traditions: Fairs and Festivals as Vessels of India's Cultural Continuity. *International Journal of Research in Social Science & Humanities*. Vol 6. Issue 8.
- [3] Blend of mythology, local culture at Ganesh pandals. (2025). *Times of India*.
- [4] De Koning, D. (2023). Green Ganesha Chaturthi: The Ritualising and Materialising of a Green Hindu Identity and the Emerging of an Alternate Representation of Ganesha. *Religions*, 14(1), Article 22.
- [5] Environmental Impact and Sustainability of Ganesh Chaturthi. (2025). *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*.
- [6] Ganesh Eco-Utsav Contest promotes environmentally friendly practices. (2024). *The CSR Journal*.
- [7] Ganpati Mandals Embrace Tradition (2025). *Times of India*.
- [8] Mohta, N. (2024). How Bal Gangadhar Tilak made Ganesh Utsav a nationalist political festival. *Indian Express Research News*.
- [9] Patel, J. A. (2024). Exploring the Ecological Significance of Ancient Indian Festivals. *Research Review Journal of Indian Knowledge Systems*. Vol 1, No. 2